

DELAMINATION IN MODE I AND II OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE MATERIALS : FIBRE ORIENTATION INFLUENCE

F. LACHAUD^{1,2}, R. PIQUET², L. MICHEL¹

² *LGMT, IUT de Génie Mécanique,
50, Chemin des Maraîchers, 31077 TOULOUSE Cedex 4, France*

¹ *ENSICA, Département Génie mécanique,
1, Place Emile Blouin 31056 TOULOUSE Cedex, France*

SUMMARY: Experimental and numerical studies of delamination in mode I and II have been carried out on thermoset and thermoplastic carbon fibre composite materials in order to determine critical energy release rates. The influence of fibre orientation around the delamination front have been studied. Results show a great influence of fibre orientation on the delamination propagation. Numerical studies are presented in order to compute energy release rates. Results are compared to experimentation.

Two applications of fracture mechanic using energy release rate values are presented. Then numerical analyses are realised. For these applications a mixed mode criterion is used. The first application concerning delamination caused by local buckling. The second one deals with delamination caused by machining and specially drilling.

KEYWORDS : Delamination, Fracture Mechanics, Finite element methods, DCB, ENF, local buckling, damage, non-linearity, drilling, machining.

INTRODUCTION

The use of the fracture mechanics criterion for design structure, require the computation of the critical energy release rate in mode I, II and III. These values are used for mixed mode criterion. More often, these values are obtained for a zero degree delamination interface [1]. Nevertheless, delamination propagation occurs between angle plies interface. The aim of this work is to show the fibre orientation importance, on the critical energy release rate values in mode I, II and III. After presenting preliminary study, we show two applications. The first application concerned the determination of propagation of delamination caused by local buckling. This damage is often find after an impact on composite structure and concerns the damage tolerance. The second one deals with the compute of delamination caused by drilling. Although composite structures are machined these operation cause lots of damage and especially delamination.

EXPERIMENTATION

Tests have been performed on a tensile machine with imposed displacement. The stacking sequence of the sample is $[\theta, -\theta, 0_8, -\theta, \theta, /, -\theta, \theta, 0_8, \theta, -\theta]$, where $(\theta=0^\circ, 22.5^\circ, 45^\circ)$. The symbol / shows the position of the initial delamination introduced during the fabrication process. The crack propagation was measured with a crack gage and a cam. An acoustic sensor has been stucked on each sample for the determination of the delamination initiation (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: DCB and ENF samples

The total energy release rate in mode I is done by the Irwin [2] relation as follow :

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{P_c^2}{2B} \cdot \frac{dC}{da} \quad (1)$$

P_c is the critical load. Load-unload cycles allow us to know the experimental compliance C versus a , when load is unloaded to zero.

The energy release rate in mode II is compute as follow :

$$G_{II} = \frac{9P^2 a^2}{2B(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \cdot C(a) \quad (2)$$

where $C(a)$ is the experimental compliance versus crack length, given by the variation of a_0 .

NUMERICAL STUDY

The numerical study has been realised with a linear and non linear 3D analysis (Fig. 2). The critical experimental displacement are introduced in the model.

Fig. 2: Mesh of the samples (DCB, ENF)

Then the total energy release rate is compute locally on the crack front by the relation :

$$G_{\text{total}}^j \underset{da \rightarrow 0}{=} - \frac{Ep(a + da) - Ep(a)}{dS} \quad (3)$$

$Ep(a)$ is the potential energy of the structure with a crack length a . $Ep(a+da)$ is the potential energy with a crack length $(a+da)$. The virtual crack extension da is created by a node displacement j . dS is the crack surface created by the local displacement of the node j (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Drawing of the perturbation node (VCE)

The energy release rate in mode I, II and III are given as followed [1,3,4] :

$$G_i^j \underset{da \rightarrow 0}{=} \frac{F_k (\lambda_k - \lambda'_k)}{2 \cdot dS} \quad (4)$$

The crack extension da is created by the length of a finite element behind the crack front. da is given by the asymptotic values of G and is between 0.025 and 0.05 a_0 . F_k ($k=1,2,3$) is the load to close the crack. λ_k et λ'_k are the local displacement in the direction i of the superposed nodes of the crack front when they are detached (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4a: Opened crack

Fig. 4b: Closed crack

Fig 4: 2D example of the MCC method

RESULTS

Results are presented for the two materials and the three stacking sequences. The development of G_{IIC}^P is curved around the crack front (Fig. 2a). The curvature increases according to the interface angle increasing. Nevertheless, the average values are very near experimental values. The partition of G_I and G_{III} , computed on DCB sample, are unimportant for the two materials. For the ENF sample, we can notice an important partition of G_I and G_{III} for $\pm 22.5^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$ interface, introducing an experimental increasing of G_{IIC}^P values (Fig. 2b).

Fig. 5a: Mode I, T300/914

Fig. 5b: % Mode II, AS4/PEEK

Fig. 5: Development of G_C along the crack front

The influence of fibres orientation around the delamination interface is indicated by an increasing ($\approx 40\%$) of G_{IC}^P (G_{IIC}^P) values between 0° interface and 45° interface (Table 1). The use of G_{IC}^P (G_{IIC}^P) values for a 0° interface, as a delamination criterion, leads to a dimensional increasing of composite structures.

Interface	G_{IC}^P exp. (N/m)	G_{IC}^P num. (N/m)	difference (%)
$0^\circ/0^\circ$	118 ¹ /1170 ²	115 ¹ /1201 ²	2.6 ¹ /2.65 ²
$\pm 22.5^\circ$	144 ¹ /1512 ²	148 ¹ /1580 ²	2.7 ¹ /4.5 ²
$\pm 45^\circ$	194 ¹ /1792 ²	202 ¹ /1994 ²	4.12 ¹ /11.0 ²

Mode I

Interface	G_{IIC}^P exp. (N/m)	G_{IIC}^P num. (N/m)	difference (%)
$0^\circ/0^\circ$	315 ¹ /1980 ²	318 ¹ /2030 ²	1.0 ¹ /2.52 ²
$\pm 22.5^\circ$	408 ¹ /1760 ²	415 ¹ /1930 ²	1.73 ¹ /9.65 ²
$\pm 45^\circ$	503 ¹ /1730 ²	530 ¹ /1960 ²	5.3 ¹ /13.0 ²

Mode II

Table 1: Numerical and experimental comparison of G_{IC}^P and G_{IIC}^P values, $a_0=40$ mm ;
(¹ T300/914 ; ² AS4/PEEK)

We can see (Table 1) the important values of G_{IC}^P and G_{IIC}^P of the AS4/PEEK material due to the important plasticity of the PEEK resin. These values are 5 to 10 more important than T300/914 material values.

APPLICATIONS

For all the applications followed, numerical studies are used to predict delamination. Numerical solutions are compared with experimental results. Only applications using carbon/epoxy composite materials is presented. For these studies, the critical energy release rate criterion used is [1] :

$$\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}} + \frac{G_{III}}{G_{IIIC}} \leq 1 \quad (5)$$

Where G_I , G_{II} are computed on the crack front for each node and G_{IC} , G_{IIC} values are those which have been calculated with DCB and ENF tests. G_{III} is negligible. Delamination occurs when the criterion is greater than 1. VCE and MCC method are used to compute these values. The numerical studies have been carried out with the help of a linear and non-linear code, SAMCEF®.

1 Application for delamination caused by local buckling

Delamination can be created by impacts on composite structures. This damage, when it appears, reduces the resistance of the structure to compressive loading, causing great difficulties for structural design (damage tolerance).

We presented a numerical study which can predict the critical load causing delamination by local buckling using fracture mechanic.

1.1 Experimentation

The compressive test samples were cut out from T300/914 carbon/epoxy plates. During the fabrication process, circular (20 mm diameter) Teflon films of 20 μ m thickness were introduced between plies of different orientation in order to create a macrodefect. Several stacking sequences are used. We only presented results for one stacking sequence :

$[45_2, //, 0_2, -45_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_s$. The sign ($//$) gives the position of the macrodefect in the thickness of the laminate.

The sample were submitted to uniaxial compressive strength measurements. During loading, the plies located under the macrodefect buckle (Fig. 6). The compressive load is stopped when the delamination propagates.

Fig. 6: Sample and experimentation

All the tests have been followed by acoustic emission in order to determine the delamination propagation.

1.2 Compute of delamination propagation

Figure 7 shows the volume mesh used for the non-linear geometric and material analysis. Numerical circular defect is created by the node duplication of the mesh in the thickness, in order to separate the plies around the delamination. A contact condition has been introduced between plies. The sample tabs are not modelled.

Numerical damage is introduced by the knowledge of the behaviour of the ply in orthotropic axes [5]. Sandhu model is used with Hashin criterion to introduce non linearity behaviour and damage appearance [5].

Fig. 7: Mesh and boundary conditions for the numerical study

More details of the procedure is done in Lachaud [5].

1.3 Results and discussion

We presented figure 8 the development of the criterion (eq. 5) for different loads. Before 30345 N, no numerical damage appears. The first damage is located in ply number 23 and develops in the ply number 24. The macrodefect occurs when an element near the crack front is completely cracked. It influence the development of the criterion as it shows on figure 8 where the criterion decreases.

Fig. 8: Numerical results for T300/914 materials, $[45_2, //, 0_2, -45_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_S$ laminate

Experimentally the delamination occurs at 37000 N and two macro-cracks are visible near the circular macrodefect (Fig. 8). Numerically, the criterion is greater than 1 (1.15) for 40450 N. Then delamination occurs for a load situated between 34700 N and 40450 N (Fig. 8). This is in good agreement with experimental results.

We can see on figure 8 that the damage of plies number 23 and 24, creates an evolution of the macro-cracks direction.

2 Application for the determination of the critical push load during drilling

For assembling or repairs of composite structures on aircraft, drilling has to be executed. During this type of machining, it can appear lots of damages. All these defects observed during drilling on composite structures with a twist drill, have been classified by W. Koëning [6]. The more important damage is the delamination [7, 8, 9]. The phenomenon occurs when the end of the drill is near the inferior face of the shell drilled.

This application of the fracture mechanic concerns the determination of the drilling critical push load of carbon/epoxy shell. A comparison between experimental and numerical studies is done.

2.1 Experimentation

All the carbon/epoxy shell have been manufactured with a Vicotex 914/T300 (Hexcel) unidirectional laminate. The stacking sequence is $[(90,45,0,-45)_3]_S$.

The twist drill use for the tests is a tungsten carbide MK20 drill.

The laminates are drilled on a numerical drilling machine, where the depth of the drilling is controlled very easily. We drilled twelve laminates in order that one, two...twelve plies stay under the twist drill. Then the laminates were put on a tensile machine (Fig. 9a). The tests consists in pushing the plies which are not drilled (Fig. 9b). The delamination occurs when the load versus transverse displacement of the drill decreases very rapidly (Fig 9b). The displacement speed is 1 mm/min.

The critical loads for all the tests are shown on figure 10

Fig. 9a: Experimentation

Fig. 9b: Behaviour of the sample

Fig. 9: Drawing of experimentation procedure

2.2 Compute of the maximal push load by finite element method

The numerical study is a linear 3D study. The numerical model presented here is available for a non-linear study as we have shown in the precedent paragraph, for delamination caused by local buckling. The mesh represents only a part of the laminate situated near the hole (Fig. 10).

The computation of energy release rate in mode I, II and III is done on the crack front. These computations permit us to use the usual criterion (shown in 1.2) combining the contributions of the different opening modes. As the precedent study, the G_{IC} and G_{IIC} values depend on the fibre orientation interface considered.

The load applied on the plies and represented the drill, is modelled first, by a local load placed on the centre of the hole, and secondly, by a pressure.

A special program written in C++ has been developed in order to find the critical load which verify the delamination criterion (eq. 5). The number of plies under the drill is updated. The local angle between ply orientation where the drill is located, is controlled in order to choice the critical values of G_{IC} and G_{IIC} .

2.3 Results and discussions

Numerical and experimental solutions are very nearby (Fig. 10). Before the seventh ply, the two numerical solution are very nearby the experimental results. After, only the solution which uses the local load, follows the experimental delamination load.

The analysis of mode I, II and III values when the criterion is verified, shows that partition of mode III is negligible. The partition of the mode II is very important when there is only a few

ply under the drill. The partition of the mode I is very important after eight plies under the drill and corresponds to 80% of the total energy release rate.

Fig. 10: Comparison between experimental and numerical analysis

CONCLUSIONS

An experimental study of fibre orientation influence on delamination propagation have been carried out for T300/914 and AS4/PEEK materials. G_{IC} and G_{IIC} values have been reached for $0^\circ/0^\circ$, $22.5^\circ/-22.5^\circ$ and $45^\circ/-45^\circ$ interface. For the two materials, critical energy release rate in mode I and II increase when the fibre orientation at delamination interface increase.

The aim of this study was to optimised a fracture mechanic criterion used to predict delamination propagation by numerical analyses.

Two application of these results have been presented. For these applications, computation of energy release rate methods have been realised for linear and non-linear analyses.

Fracture mechanics has permitted to obtain a good prediction of the load which create the delamination propagation caused by local buckling. His application for design composite structures including damage tolerance is simple and give good results. Multi-delamination have to be studied.

The use of fracture mechanics for the prediction of delamination caused by machining and particularly for drilling gives very good results comparing with experimental results. This application have to be extended with dynamic and thermal effects. The couple created by the drill has not been introduced and the local thermal effects caused by the drilling too. Experimental tests are been processing.

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